

Title of the study: Determination of Virulence Markers and Multi-Drug Resistance (MDR) among Uropathogenic *Escherichia coli* (UPEC) isolates from a Tertiary Care Hospital.

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ABSTRACT:

AIM AND OBJECTIVE: This study aimed to investigate the presence of virulence markers and multi-drug resistance (MDR) among uropathogenic *Escherichia coli* (UPEC) isolates.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted on urine specimens collected from patients clinically diagnosed with urinary tract infections (UTIs). Standard microbiological techniques were employed for the isolation and identification of *E. coli*, followed by antibiotic susceptibility testing and detection of virulence markers including siderophore production, haemagglutination, gelatinase production, serum resistance, cell surface hydrophobicity, and hemolysin production.

RESULTS: Out of 358 urine specimens, 68 *E. coli* isolates were identified, with 95.58% exhibiting MDR. All isolates showed the presence of virulence markers, with multiple markers detected in single strains. Statistical analysis revealed a significant association between virulence markers and MDR, particularly in siderophore-producing and haemagglutinating strains.

CONCLUSION: UPEC strains associated with UTIs exhibit virulence markers alongside MDR, posing challenges for treatment. Siderophore production and haemagglutination are significantly correlated with MDR. These findings underscore the importance of understanding local patterns of drug resistance for guiding empirical antibiotic therapy and addressing the complexities of UTI management.

KEYWORDS: MDR *E. coli*, Uropathogenic *E. coli*, UTI, Virulence markers of *E. coli*, siderophore production, haemagglutination production, serum resistance, cell surface hydrophobicity, hemolysin.

INTRODUCTION:

Microorganisms are known to cause various diseases. One of the most common bacterial infections affecting humans of all ages is urinary tract infections (UTI) ⁽¹⁾. UTI can be defined as a disease due to the invasion of the urinary tract by microbes. About 95% of these UTI cases are due to bacterial infection, *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) is known to cause 85% of community-acquired and 50% of hospital-acquired infections. Also, *E. coli* predominates in all age groups ⁽²⁾. The human intestinal tract has several bacterial commensals. *E. coli* is the most predominant. It can cause various infections when entering unnatural sites such as urinary tract infections being one of them. The strains isolated from such UTI cases are referred to as “Uropathogenic *E. coli*” (UPEC) ⁽³⁾. The subgroup strains are selected based on factors that facilitate the extra-intestinal survival of *E. coli* like flagella, fimbriae, etc.

Multiple virulence factors associated with *E. coli* can affect pathogenicity in combination with one another. Colonization factor, capsule, serum resistance, cell surface hydrophobicity, hemolysin, enterotoxin, siderophore, fimbriae/pili & haemagglutination are a few of them ⁽⁴⁾. The virulence markers of these UPEC strains manifest at different frequencies and distinct stages of disease ranging from asymptomatic bacteriuria to chronic pyelonephritis ⁽³⁾.

The problem worsens with the occurrence of multidrug resistance (MDR) which makes it difficult to treat these infections ⁽⁵⁾. The situation, therefore, necessitates the need to update the knowledge on the relationship between virulence markers/factors and MDR strains.

The present study therefore aims to determine the presence of virulence factors in UPEC isolates and multidrug resistance in them.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The study was conducted on urine specimens received from inpatient and outpatient departments of DVVPPF's Medical College and Hospital, Ahmednagar, Maharashtra, India.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

Patients of any gender and age group were clinically diagnosed with UTI.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

Specimens not received as per standard guidelines of the laboratory. Patients were not willing to participate in the study.

TYPE OF STUDY:

Descriptive Cross-sectional.

METHODS:

The isolation of *E. coli* was performed as per standard procedures ⁽⁶⁾. Discs for antibiotic susceptibility testing were procured from Hi-media. The antibiotic susceptibility testing was carried out by Kirby Bauer's disc diffusion method according to standard methods ⁽⁷⁾. *E. coli* ATCC 25922 was used as the control strain for identification and ABST ⁽⁷⁾.

The detection of virulence factors was carried out as follows:

1. SIDEROPHORE PRODUCTION: The Chrome Azure Sulphonate Agar (CAS) was used for the detection of the production of siderophore by *E. coli*. The CAS agar diffusion method was employed for this test. Siderophores bind to iron which is followed by chelation. The CAS-iron complex then changes its color from blue to orange ⁽⁸⁾.

2. HAEMAGGLUTINATION: The direct bacterial haemagglutination slide test was done on the isolates of *E. coli*. A drop of each red blood cell (RBC) suspension and broth culture was added to a slide. The slide was then rocked for 5 minutes at room temperature. Clumping indicated haemagglutination. Mannose-resistant haemagglutination was detected by adding 2% W/V D-mannose to the mixture of RBC and broth culture indicated by the presence of haemagglutination in this mixture ⁽⁹⁾.

3. GELATINASE PRODUCTION: Gelatin agar was used to detect the production of gelatinase. Test isolate of *E. coli* was inoculated on gelatin agar and incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. After completion of the incubation period, the plate was over-poured with a solution of tannic acid (1%). Opacity around the isolated indicated gelatinase production ⁽¹⁰⁾.

4. SERUM RESISTANCE: Colonies of *E. coli* grown overnight on blood agar plates were inoculated in Hank's balanced salt solution. 50µl of this suspension was mixed in 50µl of serum and incubated for 3 hours at 37°C. This was followed by inoculation of 10µl of this suspension on blood agar. The blood agar

plate was then incubated at 37⁰C for 24 hours. The viable count is then determined. If the colony count reduces to <1% the isolate is termed as sensitive ^(3, 1).

5. CELL SURFACE HYDROPHOBICITY: The salt aggregation test (SAT) was performed to detect this virulence factor production. A mixture of one loopful of suspension of *E. coli* isolates in phosphate buffer was mixed with an equal volume of ammonium sulfate solution of variable molarity on a glass slide. The slide was then rotated for 1 minute. SAT values of $\leq 1.25M$ showing strains of *E. coli* isolates were indicated with the production of cell surface hydrophobicity ⁽¹²⁾.

6. HAEMOLYSIN PRODUCTION: A sterile, pre-incubated, 5% sheep blood agar plate was inoculated with a test isolate of *E. coli*. Complete lysis of erythrocytes and zone of total clearance around the colonies indicated hemolysin production ^(3, 11, 12).

RESULTS:

A total of 358 urine specimens were cultured out of which 68 specimens isolated *E. coli*. Out of a total of 68 *E. coli*, 65 (95.58%) were MDR. Virulence markers and drug resistance were detected in all 68 *E. coli* isolates. Multiple virulence markers were also detected in a single isolate. Over all 271 virulence markers were detected in 68 *E. coli*. The detection of virulence markers and drug resistance in *E. coli* isolates is elaborated in Table No. 01.

TABLE NO. 01: DISTRIBUTION OF VIRULENCE MARKERS TO DRUG RESISTANCE IN (N= 68) *E. COLI* ISOLATES.

Sr. No.	VIRULENCE MARKER	TOTAL NO. OF MULTIDRUG-RESISTANT ISOLATES (%)	TOTAL NO. OF ISOLATES WITHOUT MULTIDRUG RESISTANCE (%)	NO. OF ISOLATES WITH THE VIRULENCE MARKERS (INCLUDING 271 VIRULENCE MARKERS IN 68 ISOLATES) NUMBER (%)
1	SIDEROPHORE PRODUCTION	56 (94.91)	3 (5.09)	59 (21.77)
2	HAEMAGGLUTINATION PRODUCTION	52 (96.30)	2 (3.70)	54 (19.93)
3	GELATINASE PRODUCTION	43 (93.48)	3 (6.52)	46 (16.97)
4	SERUM RESISTANCE	38(92.68)	3(7.32)	41(15.13)

5	CELL SURFACE HYDROPHOBICITY	37(92.5)	3(7.5)	40(14.76)
6	HAEMOLYSIN PRODUCTION	29(93.55)	2(6.45)	31(11.44)

Mann-Whitney U test statistic U = 36.00, p=0.0022, significant

By applying the Mann-Whitney U test there is a significant association between virulence markers

and multidrug resistance detected.

*Number of isolates producing virulence markers out of 68 *E coli* isolates.

FIGURE 01: DISTRIBUTION OF VIRULENCE MARKERS CONCERNING DRUG RESISTANCE IN 68 *E COLI* ISOLATES.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Statistical analysis was done by descriptive statistics. The descriptive analysis of independent variables (virulence markers) was carried out. The number of isolates producing virulence markers was recorded. This was followed by determining multi-drug resistance in these isolates. The percentage of the dependent variable i.e., the occurrence of MDR was calculated. Data for both variables was collected on an ordinal scale as follows.

VIRULENCE MARKER	MDR DETECTED	MDR NOT DETECTED
SIDEROPHORE	Yes	No

Similarly, data was collected for all the virulence markers (Haemagglutination production, Gelatinase production, Serum resistance, Cell surface hydrophobicity & Haemolysin production).

This was followed by elaborating on the occurrence of MDR and strains not exhibiting MDR with respect to virulence markers produced by the 68 *E. coli* isolates (Table no. 02). This information was further used to calculate the odds ratio.

TABLE NO. 02: TABLE ELABORATING DISTRIBUTION OF VIRULENCE MARKERS WITH RESPECT TO DRUG RESISTANCE.

SR. NO.	VIRULENCE MARKER	TOTAL NO. OF ISOLATES DETECTED WITH VIRULENCE MARKER	MULTIDRUG RESISTANCE DETECTED (N=65) NUMBER OF ISOLATES (%)		MULTIDRUG RESISTANCE NOT DETECTED (N= 03) NUMBER OF ISOLATES (%)	
			PRESENT A	ABSENT C	PRESENT B	ABSENT D
1	SIDEROPHORE PRODUCTION	59	56	09	03	00
2	HAEMAGGLUTINATION PRODUCTION	54	52	13	02	01
3	GELATINASE PRODUCTION	46	43	22	03	00
4	SERUM RESISTANCE	41	38	27	03	00
5	CELL SURFACE HYDROPHOBICITY	40	37	28	03	00
6	HAEMOLYSIN PRODUCTION	31	29	36	02	01

Value of $\chi^2=38.861$, $p=0.0007$, significant

By applying the Mann- Whitney U test there is a significant association between the total number of isolates expressing the virulence marker and multidrug resistance detected.

Further, the odds ratio was calculated at 95% CI to express the level of significance between the presence of virulence factor and the occurrence of MDR (Table no. 03).

TABLE NO. 03: LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE BETWEEN PRESENCE OF VIRULENCE MARKER AND OCCURRENCE OF MDR.

Sr. no.	VIRULENCE MARKER (N = 271)	ODDS RATIO	95% CI	P VALUE	REMARK
1	SIDEROPHORE PRODUCTION	2.07	0.3356-4.431	0.0124*	Expression of siderophore results in a higher risk of MDR
2	HAEMAGGLUTINATION PRODUCTION	2	0.3949-8.141	0.0103*	Higher risk
3	GELATINASE PRODUCTION	0.65	0.2401-3.218	0.9199	Lower risk of MDR
4	SERUM RESISTANCE	0.46	0.2064-2.790	0.6572	Lower risk of MDR
5	CELL SURFACE HYDROPHOBICITY	0.44	0.1998-2.707	0.6479	Lower risk of MDR
6	HAEMOLYSIN PRODUCTION	0.40	0.1942-4.155	0.6126	Lower risk of MDR

* **Significant**

Table No. 03 specifies the level of significance between the presence of virulence factor and the occurrence of MDR. The Mann-Whitney U test and Chi-square test were applied to test the association between qualitative variables at 5% (p, 0.05) and 1% (p, 0.01) levels of significance. Statistical analysis software namely SYSTAT version 12 (made by Crane's software, Bengaluru, a licensed copy was used to analyze the data.

DISCUSSION:

The most important microorganism responsible for causing urinary tract infections is uropathogenic *E. coli* (UPEC). The strains possess various specific virulence markers that enable them to invade the urinary bladder, adhere to the uroepithelial cells, and then progressively establish themselves to

cause urinary tract infection. The virulence capacity of UPEC strains is enhanced in the presence of virulence markers⁽¹³⁾. The virulence markers of *E. coli* commonly include various cell surface appendages like fimbriae, capsule, flagellum, and other membrane proteins and secreted virulence markers like siderophores and hemolysins⁽⁴⁾. The clinical outcome of UPEC strains includes 75-95% uncomplicated and 40-50% complicated UTIs. The spectrum of UTI ranges from asymptomatic bacteriuria to cystitis, pyelonephritis, and septic shock⁽⁵⁾.

The UPEC strains acquire virulence markers via the virulence genes which are chromosomally encoded⁽³⁾. The *E. coli* strains that cause UTI are also frequently multidrug resistant which aggravates the problem leaving extremely limited options for treatment^(5, 14). Hence the knowledge of the presence of common uropathogens along with virulence factors and drug resistance patterns will help to formulate an appropriate guideline for empiric antibiotic treatment. Eventually, the clinicians would be better able to deal with UTIs and hence would be beneficial for the patient.

In the present study out of 123 Gram-negative bacilli, 68 (55.284%) *E. coli* were isolated. Hence these were the commonest etiological agents to cause UTI in the present study as well. *E. coli* strains capable of producing hemolysin are commonly correlated clinically with more severe forms of UTIs. These strains are capable of damaging and causing toxic effects on a variety of host cells and are responsible for contributing towards tissue damage, and impairment of host defense mechanisms and can also cause inflammatory response⁽¹⁵⁾. In our study, we observed 31 isolates (47.69%) of *E. coli* with the production of hemolysin & amongst these 29 (93.54%,) statistically significant, were also detected to have multidrug resistance. Our findings are higher than Mittal *et al*⁽⁵⁾.

Siderophore production acts as one of the important virulence markers in the pathogenesis of urinary tract infections. It facilitates the pathogen's survival and promotes its growth in conditions where iron concentration is limited, mostly seen in phases during active infection⁽⁵⁾. In the present study 59 (86.76%) isolates were detected to produce siderophore, out of which 56 (94.91%), were MDR (statistically significant). Our findings are well in accordance with the findings of Mittal *et al*⁽⁵⁾.

Bacteria are required to adhere and eventually invade the urogenital epithelial cells to cause UTI. Bacterial appendages for attachment and adhesion play a key role in pathogenesis. Hence the ability to

produce mannose-resistant hemagglutination by UPEC strains becomes an important virulence marker ⁽¹⁶⁾. In the present study, 54 (19.93%) isolates were observed to produce hemagglutinins out of which 52 (96.30%) were multidrug resistant. Our findings are higher than Mittal *et al.* who have reported 45.5% hemagglutinin-producing strains ⁽⁵⁾.

TABLE NO. 04. ELABORATES VIRULENCE MARKERS DETERMINED IN THE PRESENT STUDY IN COMPARISON WITH OTHER INVESTIGATORS.

SR. NO.	VIRULENCE MARKER (TOTAL NUMBER OF ISOLATES EXPRESSING THE VIRULENCE MARKER)	TOTAL NO. OF ISOLATES HAVING THE PRESENCE OF VIRULENCE MARKER	OTHER INVESTIGATORS			
			MITTAL <i>ET. AL.</i> (5) N=135, (%)	JADHAV <i>ET AL.</i> (17)	RAKSHA <i>ET AL.</i> (3)	BHATTACHARYYA <i>ET AL.</i> (14)
1	SIDEROPHORE PRODUCTION	59	119 (88)	-	-	-
2	HAEMAGGLUTINATION PRODUCTION	54	101 (74.8)	45%	68 (30.9)	-
3	GELATINASE PRODUCTION	46	91 (67.5)	-	-	-
4	SERUM RESISTANCE	41	79 (59)	55%	72 (32.72)	90 (90)
5	CELL SURFACE HYDROPHOBICITY	40	82 (61)	76%	58 (26.36)	-
6	HAEMOLYSIN PRODUCTION	31	64 (47.4)	60%	91 (41.36)	10 (10)

- Not reported.

TABLE NO. 5. ELABORATES VIRULENCE MARKERS DETERMINED IN THE PRESENT STUDY CONCERNING DRUG RESISTANCE IN COMPARISON WITH OTHER INVESTIGATORS.

SR. NO.	VIRULENCE MARKER. (TOTAL NUMBER OF ISOLATES EXPRESSING THE VIRULENCE MARKER)	TOTAL NO. OF ISOLATES HAVING THE PRESENCE OF VIRULENCE MARKER	MULTIDRUG RESISTANCE DETECTED N=65 NUMBER OF ISOLATES (%)		MULTIDRUG RESISTANCE WAS DETECTED BY OTHER INVESTIGATORS. MITTAL <i>ET. AL.</i> (5)
			PRESENT	ABSENT	
1	SIDEROPHORE PRODUCTION	59	56	09	55 (46)
2	HAEMAGGLUTINATION PRODUCTION	54	52	13	16 (34.80)
3	GELATINASE PRODUCTION	46	43	22	48 (52.75)
4	SERUM RESISTANCE	41	38	27	32 (35.16)
5	CELL SURFACE HYDROPHOBICITY	40	37	28	21 (25.30)
6	HAEMOLYSIN PRODUCTION	31	29	36	13 (20.31)

There is a significant association between multidrug resistance and virulence markers. Moreover, multidrug resistance was higher and statistically significant in siderophore producing and hemagglutinating strains ($P=0.0124$ & 0.0103 respectively). Whereas multidrug resistance was observed to be comparatively less in strains producing gelatinase, hemolysin, and strains exhibiting serum resistance and cell surface hydrophobicity.

The percentage positivity of MDR in virulent UPEC strains was reported to be 69% by Shah *et al.*⁽¹⁸⁾ & 29.62% by Mittal *et al.*⁽⁵⁾. Higher resistance can be attributed to a range of factors like irrational use of antibiotics, non-compliance with antibiotics, and easy availability of over-the counter antibiotics.

CONCLUSION:

The study concludes the following:

1. UPEC stains are the most common etiological agents isolated from cases of UTI amongst other GNBs.
2. These UPEC strains exhibit the presence of one or more virulent markers.
3. The majority (95.58%) of UPEC strains exhibit one or more virulence markers and exhibit copresence of MDR.
4. Siderophore-producing and haemagglutinating UPEC strains exhibit a higher risk of acquiring MDR $P=0.0124$ & 0.0103 (statistically significant) as compared to other virulence markers.
5. Co-presence of virulence markers, and MDR shall make it more difficult for the clinicians as well as the patients to overcome the infection.
6. The data available on drug resistance could be used in formulating the appropriate antibiotic policy for treating UTIs in the present local settings.

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